

INTERLAYER CONTROL OF SiC_f/SiC COMPOSITE PREPARED BY SiC SLURRY INFILTRATION AND HOT PRESSING PROCESS

J.Y. Park*, M.H. Jeong, W.J. Kim

Dept. of Nuclear Materials Development, Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute, Daejeon, Korea

* Corresponding author (jypark@kaeri.re.kr)

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1. Introduction

SiC_f/SiC composite has potential advantages for structural applications due to its unique properties such as good irradiation resistance and thermo-mechanical properties, less severe waste generation due to neutron activation and improved plant conversion efficiencies by higher operating temperatures [1,2]. A hybrid process of SiC slurry impregnation (SI) and hot pressing (HP) has an advantage for the fabrication of dense SiC_f/SiC composite [3,4]. A typical method of the SI and HP process is a nano-infiltrated transient eutectic-phase (NITE) process [4]. In this hybrid process, effective slurry impregnation into the porous preforms using SiC slurry with various concentrations and compositions of additives is very important to increase a density of composite. Generally, the slurry impregnation is used to be performed by the vacuum method. Recently, the electrophoretic deposition (EPD) is considered as an effective slurry impregnation method for dense SiC_f/SiC composite [5,6]. But a reaction of the interlayer with the sintering additives is concerned during the SI and HP method, which could result in a damage of the interlayer and then a degradation of the composite properties.

In this study, SiC_f/SiC composites with the different types and thicknesses of the interlayers were prepared to investigate a degradation behavior of the interlayers. Two types of the interlayer were coated on the SiC fibers: single PyC or multi-(PyC and SiC) with different thickness.

2. Experimental procedure

Nano-sized β-SiC (D_m=52 nm, 97.5% pure, 620KE, Nano-Amor Inc., USA) and 12 wt% of an Al₂O₃ (D_m=150 nm, 99.9% pure, Baikowski, Japan):Y₂O₃ (D_m=220 nm, 99.99% pure, Acros Organics, USA):MgO (D_m=160 nm, 99.9% pure, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) mixture were used as the matrix phase and sintering additive, respectively. Two-dimensionally woven TyrannoTM-SA3 grade fabrics (Ube Industries LTD., Japan) were used as reinforcements after being coated with different thicknesses of the PyC and SiC layers through the decomposition of CH₄ at 1,100°C and methyltrichlorosilane (MTS, CH₃SiCl₃, 99%, Aldrich Chemical Co. Ltd.) at 1,000°C, respectively. Polyvinyl butyral (PVB) resin (Butvar B-98, Solutia, USA) was used as the binder phase. After dissolving the PVB resin in a solvent, slurries were synthesized by adding the SiC powder containing sintering additives and a polyester/polyamine co-polymeric dispersant (Hypermer KD1, ICI, UK) to the binder solution. The slurries were ball-milled using SiC balls. Two types of impregnation methods were applied for slurry impregnation into the preform; vacuum slurry impregnation (VSI) or electrophoretic deposition (EPD). For EPD, the zeta potential of the slurries was characterized using an electroacoustic-type zeta potential analyzer (Zeta Probe, Colloidal Dynamics, USA). The pH of the suspensions was adjusted using NH₄OH, CH₃COOH and HCl. The EPD was

performed using the different types of slurries for a disc-shaped SiC fabric sample, which was dipped into the slurry in the middle chamber under an applied voltage for 10 min. A dual electrode system was used for efficient impregnation from both sides. After drying the infiltrated fabrics at 70°C, 15 layers of the infiltrated fabrics were stacked with a fabric layer orientation of 0°/90° and laminated uniaxially under a pressure of 10 MPa at 80°C. Binder was burnt out at 400°C for 2 h in air. Hot pressing was carried out at 1,725 and 1,750°C in an Ar atmosphere under a pressure of 20 MPa.

The microstructural examination was carried out using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JS-5200, Jeol, Japan) at 20 KeV. The bending strength of composites was measured by a three-point flexural method. The rectangular shaped specimens with dimensions of 40 x 3 x 4 mm were cut from the hot-pressed disc. The span length and the crosshead speed for the strength measurement were 30 mm and 0.5 mm/min, respectively. The density of each sample was measured using the Archimedes method.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the density changes of vacuum slurry impregnated and hot pressed (VSI and HP) SiC_f/SiC composites at 1725°C with the thicknesses of the PyC interlayers. Fig. 2 shows the flexural strength changes and the stress-strain curves of the same composites. The density of the specimen with an interlayer thickness of 200 nm is the highest value of 2.86 g/cm³. The densities decreased with increasing the interlayer thicknesses. On the other hand, the flexural strength of composites with the interlayer thickness of less than 600 nm was around 180 MPa. As shown in Fig. 2(a), the flexural strength changes of composites with the thickness appeared not to be dependent on the density. Although the specimen with the interlayer thickness of 800 nm had a lower density, the flexural strength was the highest value of 273 MPa. Fig. 2(b) shows the stress-displacement curves of the 3-point bending test of SiC_f/SiC composites with the PyC thickness. For the thinner thicknesses of 200 and 400 nm, the curves appeared the brittle fracture mode like monolithic ceramics. As increasing the thicknesses to 600 and 800 nm, the fracture behavior

Fig. 1. Density changes of VSI and HP-SiC_f/SiC composites with thicknesses of PyC interlayers.

Fig. 2. Flexural strength changes (a) and flexural stress-crosshead displacement curves (b) of VSI and HP-SiC_f/SiC composites with thicknesses of PyC interlayers.

changed to the ductile mode with the multi-fracture steps which is a typical curve of fiber reinforced composite.

The results of the density, flexural strength and stress-stain curves of VSI-HP SiC_f/SiC composites suggest that the PyC interlayers of the specimens could be degraded. Due to the interlayer degradation, the specimen with an interlayer thickness of 200 nm seemed to show the brittle fracture mode with a lower flexural strength in spite of a high density. On the other hand, the specimen with a thicker interlayer thickness of 800 nm showed the ductile fracture mode with the multi-fracture steps and a higher flexural strength. To confirm the degradation of the interlayers, the microstructures were observed as shown in Fig. 3. The PyC interlayers (arrow marks in Fig. 3) can be observed in all specimens. But unclear boundaries between the fibers and a changed shape of the fibers were observed in the specimens with the thinner interlayer thicknesses of 200 and 400 nm. The specimen with a thicker interlayer (in Fig. 3(d)) shows a less severe degradation of interlayers.

Fig. 3. Microstructures of SiC_f/SiC composites with different thickness of PyC interlayer (arrow marks) prepared by slurry impregnation and hot pressing: (a) 200 nm, (b) 400 nm, (c) 600 nm and (d) 800 nm.

The mechanical properties of SiC_f/SiC composites are critically dependent upon the characteristics of the fiber/matrix interface [7]. Therefore, tailoring an interlayer can be a way to control the mechanical behaviors of SiC_f/SiC composites. To reduce the degradation of the interlayers during the HP process, SiC_f/SiC composites with a multi-interlayer of

(PyC+SiC) were prepared by the EPD and HP method. The coated SiC layer on the PyC interlayers seemed to be a protection layer against a reaction of PyC with sintering additives. Therefore, the degradation of the interlayers could be reduced by coating of SiC. Fig. 4 shows the density of 4 types of SiC_f/SiC composites with the single (PyC+SiC) layer and double (PyC+SiC) layers. The thickness of PyC for all composites was 200 nm and those of SiC were 200 and 600 nm, respectively. The single layer coated specimens had a higher density than the double layer coated ones. The density was decreased with increasing the SiC thickness. To get denser composite, therefore, the thickness of the SiC layer should be well controlled.

Fig. 4. Density of SiC_f/SiC composites with different types of interlayers prepared by the EPD and HP process (hot pressed at 1750°C).

Fig. 5 shows the microstructures of 4 types of SiC_f/SiC composites with single (PyC+SiC) layer ((a) and (b)) or double (PyC+SiC) layers ((c) and (d)). Most of the interlayers for all types of the specimens were remained. The degradation of the interlayers was decreased with increasing the thickness of SiC and the coating number of the (PyC+SiC) layers. This means that the SiC layers could be acted as a protection layers against the degradation of the PyC interlayers during the SI and HP process. Therefore, tailoring the interface between the fibers and the matrix of composites can

be known to be very important for the fabrication of sound composites.

Fig. 5. Microstructures of SiC_f/SiC composite with different types of the interlayers prepared by EPD and HP process: (a) single (200 nm PyC+200 nm SiC) layer, (b) single (200 nm PyC+600 nm SiC), (c) double (200 nm PyC+200 nm SiC) layers and (d) double (200 n PyC+600 nm SiC)

Summary

To investigate the degradation behavior of the interlayer during the SI+HP process, SiC_f/SiC composites with the PyC interlayers with different thickness and the (PyC+SiC) interlayers with different coating numbers were prepared. Due to the interlayer degradation, the specimens with thin PyC interlayer thicknesses of 200 nm and 400 nm showed the brittle fracture mode with a lower flexural strength in spite of a high density. By applying SiC coating on the PyC layers, however, most of the interlayers were remained for all types of the specimens, suggesting the SiC layers could be acted as a protection layer against the degradation of the PyC interlayers

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References

- [1] Douglas W. Freitag and David W. Richerson, "Opportunities for Advanced Ceramics to Meet the Needs of the Industries of the Future," DOE/ORO 2076 (1998)
- [2] T. Nozawa, T. Hinoki, A. Hasegawa, A. Kohyama, Y. Katoh, L.L. Snead, C.H. Henager Jr., J.B.J. Hegeman, "Recent advances and issues in development of silicon carbide composites for fusion applications," *J. Nucl. Mater.*, 386–388, 622- 627 (2009)
- [3] K.Y. Lim, D.H. Jang, Y.W. Kim, J.Y. Park and D.S. Park, "Fabrication of Dense 2D SiC fiber-SiC matrix composite by slurry infiltration and a stacking process," *Met. & Mater. Int.*, Vol. 14, No. 5, pp. 589-591 (2008)
- [4] Y. Katoh, S.M. Dong and A. Kohyama, "Thermo-mechanical properties and microstructure of silicon carbide composites fabricated by nano-infiltrated transient eutectoid process," *Fusion Eng. Des.*, 61-62, 723-731 (2002).
- [5] S. Novak, K. Rade, K. Konig, A.R. Boccaccini, "Electrophoretic deposition in the production of SiC/SiC composites for fusion reactor applications," *J. Europ. Ceram. Soc.*, 28 (2008) 2801–2807
- [6] J.H. Lee, G.Y. Gil and D.H. Yoon, "Fabrication of SiC_f/SiC composites using an electrophoretic deposition," *J. Kor. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 46, No. 5, pp. 447-451 (2009).
- [7] M.H. Lewis, Ch. 4.10. Interfaces in *Ceramic Matrix Composites* in: A. Kelly and C. Zweben (Eds), *Comprehensive composite materials*, Elsevier Science (2000).